

Risk Management Plan

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Achieving wider uptake of water-sm art solutions

Project number: 869283

Project duration: May 2020 – April 2024

H2020-SC5-2019-2

WWW.WIDER-UPTAKE.EU

D7.3 – Public

Risk Management Plan

VERSION

03

DATE

14-February-2022

ABSTRACT

This deliverable provides an overview of the risks foreseen in the project and the measures in place to reduce them. It builds on the risk management plan provided in the project proposal and it is updated as the project proceeds to the execution phase.

The risk management plan of WIDER UPTAKE uses a standard tool from SINTEF (in excel format) where risks and mitigating measures are identified in a structured process. This report shows the outcome of the standard tool.

A revised Risk Management Plan (version 03) has been prepared to include two additional risks that were discussed during the project review after the 1st Reporting Period. These are 1) risks of not providing planned deliverables due to failure linked to some technical applications on the demonstration sites, and 2) risk of not achieving the foreseen impact due to non-social acceptance of water reuse on the demonstration sites.

DELIVERABLE ID

D7.3

WORK PACKAGE

WP7

PLANNED DELIVERY DATE

14-February-2022

AUTHORSHIP AND APPROVAL INFORMATION

LEAD BENEFICIARY

SINTEF

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RELEASE HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	VERSION DESCRIPTION/MILESTONE* DESCRIPTION
01	06-July-2020	Version released for PMT comments
02	30-July-2020	Revised draft version for submission
03	14-February-2022	Revised version after project review for RP1

My project - Follow-up plan

Risk reduction measures

Project name: WIDER UPTAKE

Date: 2022-02-14

Project leader: Herman Helness (SINTEF)

Deliverable number: D7.3

Deliverable name: Risk Management plan

Work package: WP7

Project values that require safeguarding	Topic/risk factor	Describe risk	Level of risk	Potential consequences	Actions	Responsibility	Deadline/frequency	Comments
Deliverables	Data availability	Delays in data acquisition, lack of data transfer permissions, relevant data not recorded, poor data quality, wrong format or not serving the purpose	Medium	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results, limited possibility for tool validation	Involvement of local industry participants and stakeholders in planning and execution of data collection from day one. Early dialog between WP's sharing data with focus on data quality and timing. Active presence of WP1 lead.	PMT	Monthly follow-up at PMT meetings	Innovations in WIDER UPTAKE have sufficiently high TRL to ensure that development is not done from scratch.
Deliverables	Client-related or external terms of reference	Lost of key partner	Low	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results, limited impact of project results	Follow provisions in the Consortium Agreement allowing the co-ordinator to intervene and initiate corrective actions to address problems, reallocate a partner's task and, if needed, include new partners with suitable skills and profiles.	Coordinator	As deemed necessary	
Deliverables	Client-related or external terms of reference	Lack of some stakeholder involvement	Low	Delays in project execution, limited impact of project results, limited learning among cases and countries	Involve stakeholders in planning of the activities during the initial phase of the project. Involve stakeholders in the activities in a structured manner by way of the CoP.	PMT	Monthly follow-up at PMT meetings	Decision level commitment was secured in the proposal phase by way of letters of commitment.
Deliverables	Organisational complexity	Collaboration problems in the Consortium	Low	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results, limited learning among cases and countries	Secure involvement of all participants in planning and executing activities. Ensure representation of all participants in governing bodies. Regular communication with all participants during project execution.	PMT	Monthly follow-up at PMT meetings	There are clear rules concerning IPR in the Consortium Agreement to safeguard potential issues.
Deliverables	Organisational complexity	Poor communication between consortium partners, unclear responsibility distribution for progress in the case studies, operate as independent subprojects rather as one project	Medium	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results, limited learning among cases and countries	Secure involvement of all participants in planning and executing activities. Ensure fluid internal communication and information sharing. Ensure active operation of the Communities of practice.	PMT	Monthly follow-up at PMT meetings	
Deliverables	Project schedule	Failure of a partner to perform according to the project plan and time schedule	Medium	Delays in project execution	All participants in the consortium are familiar with the type of activity they are responsible for. Allocate clear responsibilities in the WP's and tasks.	WP leads	Regular WP meetings as deemed necessary and monthly PMT meetings	
Deliverables	Personnel resources	Lost of key staff	Low	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results	Ensure that knowledge about innovations and activities is spreaded throughout the team. Avoid WP or tasks to be dependent on a single partner, to allow easy involvement of other partner if needed.	Partner losing key staff.	As deemed necessary	Most of partners are large organisations and will be able to replace staff with equivalent personnel if needed
Deliverables	Personnel resources	Shortage of personnel	Low	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results	Action to be taken if needed (partner lacking resources to communicate about challenges as early as possible to Coordinator). Provisions are in place in the Consortium agreement if re-allocation of tasks between partners is necessary.	Partner lacking personnel resources.	Monthly follow-up at PMT meetings	

Deliverables	Financial framework/budget	Shortage of financial resources	Low	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results	Action to be taken is needed (partner lacking financial resources to communicate as early as possible challenges to Coordinator). Provisions are in place in the Consortium agreement if re-allocation of budget between partners if necessary.	Partner lacking financial resources.	Monthly follow-up at PMT meetings	
Deliverables	Project schedule	Failure in project execution due to unexpected challenges	Medium	Delays in achieving milestones or preparing deliverables	Regular project monitoring and communication with the WP-leaders to ensure that any challenges are detected at an early stage. Ensure that clear responsibilities are allocated in the WP's and tasks. If challenges are detected, prepare a contingency plan to mitigate the failure with the parties involved. The governing bodies of the project will be involved according to provisions set out in the Consortium Agreement, which will regulate how to respond to different levels of failure with respect to which decision bodies that should be			
Deliverables	Skills and expertise	Poor quality of work	Low	Low quality of results, limited impact of project results, loss of reputation for all project partners	Procedures for quality assurance established by month 3. Project reports will be QA by two independent parties. The project has a dedicated QA responsible who will ensure good quality of deliverables. The Project Advisory Committee will contribute to secure the scientific quality of project results and provide input in scientific issues in the project.	Coordinator	QA for project deliverables as scheduled.	
Deliverables	Communication & dissemination	Limited interest in the project content and results	Medium	Limited project impact	The communication plan and the dissemination plan will be updated on a regular basis as part of task 7.4 and WP6 respectively. In case of low interest in the project, the communication strategy will be revised, and additional, more targeted communication channels will be used.	Task 7.4 lead and WP6 lead		
Personnel safety	Personnel transport	Transport by road to treatment plants	Medium	Personnel injured and/or material losses	Ensure HSE regulations are in place, communicated to all personnel involved and followed	Case owners		Moderate road distances in the Italian cases
Personnel safety	Business travels	International meetings at Consortium and WP level with potential risk for health (due for example to Covid-19)	Medium	Exposure to diseases and unwanted travel changes	Follow-up HSE regulations to avoid risk for exposure. Substitute physical meetings with digital meetings when deemed necessary.	All		
Personnel safety	Lab work/fieldwork	HSE unwanted events at the demonstration sites or at laboratories	Low	Personnel injured and/or material losses	Ensure HSE regulations are in place, communicated to all personnel involved and followed.	Case owners and partners performing lab work		
Personnel safety	Business travel	(Potentially) travels outside EU (Ghana)	Low	Personnel injured and/or material losses	Ensure HSE regulations are in place, communicated to all personnel involved and followed.	All		Specific travel regulations have to be checked, eg., vaccination, visa, etc.
Deliverables	Failure linked to some technical applications	Failure to provide the planned deliverables on time due to technical failure of some technical processes at the demonstration cases	Medium	Delays in project execution, lower quality of results, limited possibility for tool validation	Involvement of local industry participants and stakeholders in planning and execution of technical demonstrations from day one. Early dialog between WP participants and Task leaders to inform of any issues. Active presence of WP1 lead and coordinator.	PMT	Monthly follow-up at PMT meetings	

